

Stakeholder Engagement Plan

RDNL Training and Community Platform.
WP4 Governance and Sustainability.

About this document

This document was established by a dedicated task group within Research Data Netherlands (RDNL), in consultation with RDNL members, a selection of training providers, and individual data stewards. This is version 1.0, established as a first deliverable in December 2025 of an Open Science NL-funded project (2025-2028). The document will be updated at regular intervals after broader evaluation by key stakeholders. A final version will be published before the end of the RDNL project in 2028.

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1. Introduction

The main goal of the stakeholder engagement plan is to identify, engage and consult the right people over the course of the project so that the RDNL National Training and Community Platform (NTP) is successfully supported by the key stakeholders, with the aim to result in sustainable scenarios beyond the project lifetime.

The vision of the project is to contribute to the transition towards open science by increasing the capacity of data stewards in the Netherlands, not just in terms of the number of capable data stewards, but also in their enhanced skills and competences. We believe that research will improve from a collaboration between researchers and well-trained, qualified data professionals. The goal of the stakeholder engagement plan is to mobilise our key stakeholders to endorse/share our vision and become actively involved in our activities and in sustaining the RDNL platform. This also helps to optimally position the platform in the rapidly developing open science and research data landscape, aligned within Europe (e.g. in the framework of the development of the European Open Science Cloud and other European Data Spaces).

This engagement plan focuses on key stakeholders for the work package on governance and sustainability of the platform. Other work packages in the project will have their own engagement activities to meet their respective deliverables and we will ensure that our activities are aligned across work packages. Over the course of the project, engagement activities will be streamlined where possible so as not to overburden overlapping stakeholders.

This Stakeholder Engagement Plan is a living document to be reviewed annually (when necessary) and adjusted to reflect project progress and evolving stakeholder needs.

2. Stakeholder analysis

When thinking about governance and sustainability of a national training and community platform, who exactly are the stakeholders and what power and influence do they have?

Figure 1 maps out the stakeholder(s) and groups which are key to engage with over the course of this project. The stakeholder mapping¹ helps to assess and categorise stakeholders based on their level of interest and influence. It enables us to tailor engagement strategies, accordingly, depending on the interest and power of identified stakeholders.

The project's stakeholder base is broad, encompassing all institutes/organisations that can contribute towards finetuning the project deliverables as well as the users of the national platform (including trainers/coaches and the broader community). In this mapping exercise we only focus on the stakeholders which are key to the milestones and deliverables for governance and sustainability.

Figure 1 categorises each stakeholder (group), their role and the (mutual) benefit of their engagement:

Key players (high power, high interest): These are the most influential and interested stakeholders. Close collaboration is essential, mainly through face-to-face interaction via meetings and events. They also receive regular, online updates.

- ▶ Academic and research institutes (RPOs, research performing organisations). This group primarily covers the universities, the University Medical Centres and the Universities of Applied Sciences. They are the employers of the research data professionals, and they require members of their professional staff to be (continuously) upskilled on different aspects of research data management. They have insight in the competences that are needed for their staff. The engagement needed from this stakeholder is input into the curriculum, adoption of the training programme, and recognition of the certification. In addition, their role is crucial to establish a long-term partnership with the national platform. Finally, it is important to realise that the RPOs have several different roles. Next to the role as employer, the RPOs host the Local Digital Competence Centres (LDCCs), which have a crucial role in the organisation of the data stewardship landscape in the Netherlands. In addition, the RPOs are also training providers (see below).
- ▶ Open Science NL (part of NWO): as the funding authority, Open Science NL (OSNL) ensures that project is delivered efficiently and successfully. OSNL is also a strategic driver that can influence key decisions and have a strong interest in achieving the intended outcomes. OSNL can ensure alignment with the national Open Science Agenda and contribute to embedding the platform in other national OSNL structures.

1 Inspiration for Figure 1: Stakeholder Mapping is drawn from: [EOSC-Life Strategic Marketing and Stakeholder Mapping Report](#)

- ▶ **OSNL partners:** the partners or ‘Strategy Council’ of OSNL are a group of 16 organisations that have a shared interest in the project as part of the overall OSNL aims and work programme². These organisations, which include those involved in RDNL (4TU.ResearchData, SURF, DANS, Health-RI), support the project by providing expertise and are a key group for gathering consensus about governance and sustainability. OSNL partners help ensure that outcomes align with strategic needs and standards for the sector. Their interest lies in achieving impact, and some might be involved in future governance models for the platform. In view of their role in overseeing other related initiatives that strengthen Open Science and arrange for a consolidated research data landscape, this group is the primary stakeholder group to help optimise the position of the RDNL platform towards a sustainable activity embedded in the national research (data) landscape.
- ▶ **(Local) training providers (TP):** The TP provide training content and expertise and often have a running training programme/portfolio. Examples are: eScience Center, LDCCs. Their engagement is crucial to define a truly national programme, based on a common understanding and agreement about the national curriculum. Their role is to contribute to the identification on the training needs (gap analysis), map their course(s) on the curriculum, to fill the national training portfolio and work together towards a delivery model for the Netherlands for this portfolio. This could also entail co-developing new courses together. These actors contribute practical skills and hands-on experience. They could contribute to skills development and capacity-building activities via this platform which contributes to on-going sustainability, and in turn they benefit from the national positioning of this platform.

Keep satisfied (low power, high interest): These stakeholders have less influence but have a high interest in the success of the training platform. As a result, they will be consulted on relevant topics and invited to events, as well as engaged through online updates.

- ▶ **Data stewards/data professional communities:** these are the end users of the trainings and as such the primary beneficiaries of the NTP. They are a key stakeholder to consult in all phases of the project, and they are also crucial to install the feedback loop. The feedback loop will ensure the needs of the communities are considered and prioritised in the development and delivery of the Training Programme. In turn, the platform provides the potential to be a one-stop shop for these communities for most of their training and community needs.
- ▶ **Representatives of thematic communities:** they bring insight into local needs, priorities, and challenges from a domain perspective (e.g. via the three Dutch Thematic Digital Competence Centres (TDDCs) for life sciences and health, social sciences and humanities, and natural and engineering sciences). They ensure the project remains relevant and appropriate, while fostering engagement and connection among different thematic communities. The TDCCs and their respective host organisations (DANS-KNAW, 4TU.ResearchData and Health-RI) are foreseen to bring in the

2 OSNL Strategy Council: <https://www.openscience.nl/en/strategy-council>

more advanced domain specific trainings, that can build on the 'basic' curriculum that will be formulated by RDNL. In that way appropriate Learning Paths become available for the end-user.

Keep informed (high power, low interest): These stakeholders have high power but lower interest. They should be actively engaged to gain their support.

- ▶ Executive Boards (academic and research institutes): this stakeholder group might not be aware of the immediate value of the platform, but they have the power to influence its long-term success. It will be important to seek commitment from this group to sustaining the RDNL training and community platform, as it will provide the relevant upskilling that will have a positive impact on research and education within their respective institutes.

Monitor (low power, low interest): These stakeholders include representatives from similar initiatives, industry and/or community. These groups will be monitored to see if they gain any power and interest and hence the need to actively engage them. In addition to this, these are stakeholders that the project can learn from in the coming years and try to incorporate any best practices within the platform.

- ▶ Skills and training related work in international initiatives like European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and Research Data Alliance (RDA) will be followed closely. This will prevent reinventing the wheel and will ensure that we adopt the newest international insights related to setup training in data stewardship, including e.g. standards for metadata and methods of certification.

In later phases of the project, we may consider engaging additional stakeholders if their input becomes relevant, such as KNAW institutes, TO2 institutes, governmental knowledge institutes, and a range of local training providers.

Figure 1: Stakeholder Mapping

3. Key Milestones and Deliverables

Over the duration of the project, key activities will be organised to successfully meet the planned milestones and deliverables for WP4 (see Figure 2). These activities will engage the different stakeholder groupings identified in our stakeholder analysis. The two main areas of focus will be governance and sustainability, although these are interlinked and the outputs of each of these areas will inform one another.

Figure 2: Overview of key milestone and deliverables

The table below summarises each milestone and deliverable and the respective deadline indicated in months (M) and year (YR) of the project. Stakeholder engagement activities will be thought out and planned in such a way to best meet these milestones and deliverables.

Milestone/Deliverable	Description	Deadline (month/year)
Exploitation Overview (Milestone 4.2)	<p>The exploitation overview will summarise platform costs, user experience and feedback, IP considerations, and revenue from course fees. This overview will be discussed at the end of year 2 to kick start the engagement process with key stakeholders to design a future proof business model for the platform.</p>	M20, YR 2 (2026)
Platform Governance Options Paper Document (Deliverable 4.2)	<p>There are several possible scenarios to guarantee an organisation and governance model through which key stakeholders as well as community needs can drive the Platform. The governance options paper describes agreed governance principles, potential governance models and outlines recommendations and steps for implementation.</p>	M30, YR 3 (2027)
Platform Sustainability Plan (Deliverable 4.3)	<p>Based on the first exploitation overview, scenarios will be developed for a Platform Sustainability Plan which will include exploring revenue models using the running platform as a benchmark and comparing it to other local and international training programmes.</p>	M36, YR 3 (2027)
Governance Model Chosen (Milestone 4.3)	<p>A final governance model (from the options paper and scenarios) will be chosen and will be the focus of the transition plan.</p>	M36, YR 3 (2027)
Transition to future governance (Milestone 4.4)	<p>A suitable governance will be in place before the end of the project. This will mark the transition from the current RDNL project structure to future governance.</p>	M45, YR 4 (2028)

4. Stakeholder Engagement Activities

In order to effectively meet our key deliverables and milestones, the table below maps out the planned stakeholder activities. The activities are indicated per quarter of the project year. An overarching goal per year is included to align all the planned activities within that year.

For each type of stakeholder group, key contact persons from within relevant organisation/institute and community will be identified. A comprehensive contact list will be developed and maintained during the project so that our engagement activity per stakeholder is identified and tracked. The activities planned for year 2 (2026) have been more fully developed and described in detail. Activities for subsequent years will be elaborated and refined as the project progresses.

We aim to use the following methods to engage with specific stakeholders:

With external stakeholders: annual stakeholder forum, thematic meetings, workshops, interviews, website news and blogposts and so forth.

Table Stakeholder Engagement Activities

Engagement Focus	Stakeholder Representatives	Engagement Method	Purpose	Estimated timeline (Quarter/ Month/ Year)
Year 1 (2025): Initiation & Setup				
Overall Goal: Understanding the current landscape and identifying relevant stakeholders.				
Establish Project Stakeholder Forum	Key Players	In-person Forum meeting	Stakeholder forum kick-off and forging long term relationships with partners First RDNL Stakeholder Forum - RDNL	30 September 2025 (due M12)
Pilot interviews	Key Players/Keep Satisfied	In-person interviews	Understand how training is currently organised and what the wishes are for the future.	Q1, Q2
Stakeholder Engagement Plan	Internal project members	Internal review process	Refine roles according to project phases and stakeholder groups, and outline channels and opportunities for engagement by these groups throughout the project and mapping this in a comprehensive Stakeholder Engagement Plan .	Q4 Deliverable 4.1 (due M12)
Year 2 (2026): First generation exploitation overview				
Overall Goal: Bringing diverse stakeholders on board to co-create and understand our joint vision.				
Internal collaboration with project work packages 1, 2 & 3	Internal project members	Meetings	Input from WP1, WP2 & WP3 will inform the pilot interviews. These WPs have insight into actual costs and revenues for the platform.	Q1, Q2

Engagement Focus	Stakeholder Representatives	Engagement Method	Purpose	Estimated timeline (Quarter/ Month/ Year)
Year 2 (2026): First generation exploitation overview				
Overall Goal: Bringing diverse stakeholders on board to co-create and understand our joint vision.				
Interviews	Key Players	One on one (in-person or virtual)	Discuss, explore in detail, funding/revenue models, particularly at academic and research institutes. Explore their willingness to endorse, co-create and contribute (in-kind and financially) for a training platform and their expectations for such training vs. costs.	Q1, Q2
Consultations	Monitor	One on one (in-person or virtual)	Explore other initiatives (locally, internally or industry) to gather a sense of their governance and sustainability models for their training.	Q2, Q3
Workshop	Key Players		Endorsement of vision and commitment to contribute and collaborate on a National Training Platform.	Q2
Exploitation Overview Consultation	Key Players	Thematic workshop	Present and get input on initial cost and revenue estimates, possible models on offer (subscriptions, or memberships), funding sources and a comparison with existing platforms, commercial offerings, etc.	Q3

Engagement Focus	Stakeholder Representatives	Engagement Method	Purpose	Estimated timeline (Quarter/ Month/ Year)
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Year 2 (2026): First generation exploitation overview

Overall Goal: Bringing diverse stakeholders on board to co-create and understand our joint vision.

Stakeholder Forum	Key Players	In-person Forum meeting	Present a stakeholder-validated, comprehensive first generation exploitation overview (Milestone 4.2) . The presentation would include: A summary of input from thematic meetings and consultations, key priorities, concerns, and opportunities raised by stakeholders, mapping of possible options for contribution for sustainability (financially, operationally, or strategically).	Q4 Milestone 4.2 (due M20)
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Communication about the sustainability of the platform	All Stakeholder groups	Blog posts, e-mails	Start to position the National Platform and create buy in.	Q3, Q4
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Year 3 (2027): Platform Governance Options and finalisation

Overall Goal: Exploring and summarising various sustainability and governance options

Sustainability Scenario workshop	Key Players		Discuss different revenue models: fee-for-service, subscription, paid membership, or hybrid approaches and how each will be feasible, financially viable and aligned to the current strategic goals for academic institutes.	Q1
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Engagement Focus	Stakeholder Representatives	Engagement Method	Purpose	Estimated timeline (Quarter/ Month/ Year)
Year 3 (2027): Platform Governance Options and finalisation				
Overall Goal: Exploring and summarising various sustainability and governance options				
Field Survey	Key Players/ Keep satisfied	Via e-mail	The results of the field survey will be summarised on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ willingness to pay, training needs, and operational support (based on concrete scenarios); ▶ risks/benefits analysis; ▶ feasibility given field survey input. 	Q2
Stakeholder Forum	Key Players	In-person Forum meeting	Presenting and summarising field survey results and final sustainability scenario plans for input/discussion. Based on discussion, a final output will be prepared: A platform Governance Options Paper (Deliverable 4.2).	Q3 Deliverable 4.2 (due M30)
Engaging with Executive Leadership	Keep satisfied	Information sessions/ road shows	Presenting/creating buy in on the platform governance options and aligning and presenting clear value proposition for their data professionals.	Q4
Communication about the sustainability of the platform	All Stakeholder groups	Blog posts, e-mails	Continue to position the National Platform.	Q1-Q4

Engagement Focus	Stakeholder Representatives	Engagement Method	Purpose	Estimated timeline (Quarter/ Month/ Year)
Year 4 (2028): Sustainability & Transition				
Overall Goal: Finalisation of governance and transitioning from project to chosen governance model.				
Stakeholder Forum	Key Players	Virtual/in-person	Presentation of all options as well as a risk/benefit analysis and a final selection of the Platform Sustainability Plan (Deliverable 4.3) .	Q1 Deliverable 4.3 (due M36)
Governance co-design workshop	Key Players, internal project members	Virtual/in-person	Post project governance model chosen: roles, responsibilities governance, financial aspects and use this to draft a transition plan. Governance Model Chosen (Milestone 4.3) .	Q1, Q2 Milestone 4.3 (due M36)
Transition plan consultations	Key Players, internal project members	Virtual	Use online review sessions/e-mail feedback to finalise the Transition from project structure to future governance (Milestone 4.4) .	Q3 Milestone 4.4 (due M45)
Stakeholder Forum	All Stakeholders	In-person Forum meeting		Q4

5. Collecting and incorporating feedback

To ensure transparency and accountability, all stakeholder interactions and feedback will be systematically recorded. We will record the following:

- ▶ Participant attendance: Maintain a register of attendants to meetings, consultations and mailing list for e-mail communications;
- ▶ After direct engagement activities, maintain a summary of key takeaways and recommendations;
- ▶ Issues and opportunities raised through engagement activities can be escalated to the WP co-leads or the RDNL Board if needed.

6. Conclusion

The stakeholder engagement plan is a dynamic document that highlights the key engagement activities planned over the course of the project. This plan therefore is not a static document and will be reviewed annually and updated if necessary to ensure it incorporates the latest developments in the open science and research data landscape, in order to meet the upcoming milestones and deliverables.

Research Data Netherlands is a national coalition of 4TU.ResearchData, DANS, Health-RI and SURF.

